

Managing Editor's Column

Dear Readers,

welcome to the ninth issue of volume 13. I want to thank all authors for their contributions and the editorial board for their review effort. I hope you will enjoy the papers.

This issue contains 13 articles: P. Adamopoulou, E. Sakkopoulos, A. Tsakalidis, M.D. Lytras: Web Service Selection based on QoS Knowledge Management; S. Arroyo: Ontology and Grammar of the SOPHIE Choreography Conceptual Framework - An Ontological Model for Knowledge Management; S. Colucci, T. Di Noia, E. Di Sciascio, F.M. Donini, A. Ragone: Semantic-based Skill Management for Automated Task Assignment and Courseware Composition; J.M. Doderó, S. Sánchez-Alonso, D. Frosch-Wilke: Generative Instructional Engineering of Competence Development Programmes; M.T. Afzal, N. Kulathuramaiyer, H. Maurer: Creating Links into the Future; L. Li, V. Bulitko, R. Greiner: Focus of Attention in Reinforcement Learning; Y. Baleghi Damavandi, K. Mohammadi: A. Settle, C. Settle: Distance Learning and Student Satisfaction in Java Programming Courses; J.A. Troyano, F. Enríquez, F. Cruz, J.M. Cañete-Valdeón, F.J. Ortega: Improving the Performance of a Tagger Generator in an Information Extraction Application; Y. Baleghi Damavandi, K. Mohammadi: Co-evolution for Communication: An EHW Approach; H. Liu, A. Abraham: An Hybrid Fuzzy Variable Neighborhood Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm for Solving Quadratic Assignment Problems; J. Tao, N. Wang, X. Wang: Genetic Algorithm Based Recurrent Fuzzy Neural Network Modeling of Chemical Processes; Y. Wang, Z. Zhang, J. Cui: The Architecture and Circuital Implementation Scheme of a New Cell Neural Network for Analog Signal Processing; J. Yang, T. Li, S. Liu, T. Wang, D. Wang, G. Liang: Computer Forensics System Based on Artificial Immune Systems;

Yours sincerely,

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Graz / Austria, September 28, 2007
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